
MATERNAL GAIT CONTRIBUTES TO DEVELOPMENT OF BEAT PERCEPTION AND URGE TO MOVE TO MUSIC IN A PREDICTIVE PROCESSING NETWORK MODEL

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ABSTRACT

Humans uniquely perceive periodic structure in complex rhythms and spontaneously move to music—abilities rare among animals. Though training and experience contribute to our sense of rhythm, basic beat perception and the urge to move to rhythm are present even in young infants. But might prenatal experience play an essential role in shaping these faculties? We propose that maternal gait during pregnancy provides critical scaffolding for rhythm development through correlated auditory-vestibular inputs that train predictive neural circuits. We implemented a recurrent predictive coding network with parallel vestibular and auditory sensory pathways, trained via Hebbian learning to minimize prediction error. Training paired discrete auditory pulses with continuous triangular vestibular waveforms mimicking maternal locomotion. These networks learned to anticipate beats and spontaneously generated vestibular predictions from auditory-only input, which, under the principles of active inference, are expected to evoke bodily movement. Critically, continuous vestibular input was necessary for successful training. This input bridges temporal gaps between auditory events, solving the credit assignment problem that makes rhythm learning computationally difficult. The resulting rhythm-induced vestibular predictions offer a possible explanation for why humans spontaneously move to music. This work illustrates how simple sensory correlations during development can give rise to complex musical behaviors.

Keywords predictive coding · rhythm perception · active inference · sensorimotor synchronization · developmental neuroscience · maternal gait

1 Introduction

Humans have a remarkable ability to perceive rhythmic periodicity in music and a strong inclination to synchronize their movements to it. This perception of rhythmic structure and the spontaneous urge to move in response are fundamental to musical behavior and ubiquitous across human cultures. Notably, this capacity appears to be rare in the animal kingdom: even our closest primate relatives need extensive training to move along with external rhythmic patterns, underscoring the unique evolutionary trajectory of rhythm skills in humans [1, 2]. Research on sensorimotor development during the perinatal period reveals that fetuses display rhythmic motor patterns and can predict event timing in isochronous and metrical auditory sequences [3, 4, 5], suggesting that rhythmic capacities undergo significant development before postnatal experience. The influence of cultural experience and musical training on these abilities [6] demonstrates that rhythm perception is shaped by experience. Since rhythm is so clearly influenced by postnatal experience, it suggests that prenatal experience may also play a formative role in development. However, it remains unclear whether these experiential effects build upon innate dedicated beat-tracking circuitry, or if the circuitry is more general and beat-tracking itself emerges as a result of experience.

This raises two distinct but potentially connected questions: 1) How does prenatal experience contribute to the development of rhythm perception? and 2) Why do we spontaneously move when we perceive rhythmic patterns? These seemingly separate phenomena may share common underlying mechanisms that have yet to be fully elucidated.

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One influential evolutionary account addressing these questions is the Bipedal Hypothesis of rhythmic entrainment [7]. Larsson proposes that the advent of bipedal locomotion – and the predictable self-generated sounds it produces (regular footfalls, breathing, etc.) – created conditions that favored the evolution of timing mechanisms for detecting periodicity. According to this hypothesis, because walking on two legs generates steady auditory patterns, our ancestors’ brains may have become “primed” to expect rhythmic input and align movement with it. This bipedal hypothesis provides a compelling backdrop for why humans, unlike quadrupedal apes, evolved spontaneous synchronization to rhythmic stimuli. However, it doesn’t explain how an individual human (especially a pre-walking infant) actually develops the ability to align movement with auditory rhythmic patterns, nor why we feel a spontaneous urge to move when we hear them.

A significant clue comes from research on multisensory rhythm perception. When infants are bounced to a rhythm, their auditory perception changes – for example, bouncing on every second versus every third auditory event causes infants to encode the pattern in duple (march) or triple (waltz) meter [8]. This finding indicates a “strong, early-developing interaction between auditory and vestibular information” in the brain that may provide the foundation for both rhythm perception and the spontaneous urge to move.

Despite growing interest in this area, there remains a significant gap in our understanding of how the relationship between vestibular and auditory systems supports both rhythm perception and movement synchronization during development. Traditional models of rhythm processing often focus on auditory information alone and thus do not elucidate how infants learn to both perceive and move to rhythmic patterns through experience.

In this paper, we address these questions by building a computational model of how rhythm perception and synchronization may develop in humans. Our approach is based on the theory of Predictive Processing [9], which proposes that the brain works as a prediction machine – constantly anticipating what it will experience next and comparing these predictions with actual sensory input. When predictions don’t match reality, the brain updates its models and may trigger movements to resolve these mismatches. Further, under active inference, agents move to fulfill their sensory predictions, thereby minimizing prediction error through action rather than updating internal models [10]. This framework provides a natural way to think about both how we learn to perceive rhythmic structure and why we move to it.

Our model simulates an infant-like agent that experiences the sensory consequences of maternal gait – rhythmic auditory stimuli and corresponding movement sensation – gradually learning to anticipate periodic auditory events and coordinate its movements with them. By showing how both rhythm perception and the urge to move can emerge from the same learning process, we bridge the gap between evolutionary theory and developmental reality. Specifically, we demonstrate how the auditory and vestibular stimulation arising from maternal gait during pregnancy could train a fetal brain to both perceive rhythmic patterns and spontaneously move to them after birth.

This account not only addresses missing pieces of the bipedal hypothesis but also offers broader insight into how predictive mechanisms might underlie the human capacity for rhythm, with potential implications for understanding developmental conditions affecting rhythm perception and production.

2 Model Foundation

Our model is grounded in the principles of predictive processing and active inference, which provide a powerful framework for understanding the development of rhythm perception and movement synchronization. In this section, we outline the theoretical underpinnings of our approach and justify our modeling choices.

2.1 Predictive Processing and Rhythm Perception

Rhythm perception can be conceptualized as dynamic inference of the state of an internal model, continually refined through prediction error minimization [11, 12, 12, 13, 14]. The brain generates predictions about when auditory events will occur based on internal models of temporal structure. When this internal model reaches specific states, it predicts corresponding auditory events in a rhythmic pattern. These predictions flow downward through top-down neural pathways toward sensory areas, while sensory information flows upward. Mismatches between predictions and actual sensory input generate prediction errors, which drive three processes: the evolution of the internal model, perceptual learning, and action generation [15].

This predictive framework naturally accounts for how the brain extracts periodic structure from complex auditory signals by continuously anticipating future events. It also explains how these predictions become increasingly precise with experience, as the internal model is refined through learning to minimize prediction errors. Importantly, such internal models are not limited to auditory processing but extend to multimodal integration.

2.2 Vestibular-Auditory Integration in Rhythm Processing

When cyclically patterned rhythmic auditory stimulation arrives in coordination with cyclical vestibular input, principles of Predictive Processing suggest that our internal model of beat-based rhythm will come to predict not only auditory events but also corresponding cycles of vestibular stimulation. We hypothesize that this integration is shaped in part through experience in utero: the vestibular system becomes functional early, allowing fetuses to experience vestibular stimulation from maternal movement, particularly walking, for months before birth [16, 17]. Critically, this vestibular input is temporally correlated with auditory input from maternal footsteps.

Our model proposes that the fetal brain learns an internal model of rhythm from this correlated input, and this internal model comes to predict both auditory and vestibular sensations that occur rhythmically. This learning persists after birth, and allows purely auditory rhythmic patterns (such as music) to activate vestibular predictions based on learned associations.

2.3 Active Inference and Movement Generation

The active inference framework provides a compelling mechanism for explaining how predictions become movements. Under this framework, motor actions are not commanded directly but arise from predictions of proprioceptive and vestibular sensations [10]. When we predict a cycle of vestibular input but don't receive it, we resolve this prediction error through the most straightforward means available: moving our bodies to create the expected vestibular input cycle—in other words, moving to the rhythm.

This explains the spontaneous urge to move when we hear rhythmic patterns: our brain predicts not only upcoming auditory events but also the vestibular and proprioceptive sensations that have been associated with that rhythm throughout development. These sensory predictions effectively function as motor commands, triggering movements that would produce those expected sensations. Rather than viewing movement as a separate response to auditory rhythm, active inference frames it as an integral part of the predictive process itself.

2.4 Learning Mechanisms and Developmental Trajectories

How does the internal model, capable of continuing a cycle filling the time between auditory events in order to predict subsequent events, develop? Predictive processing theory suggests that learning proceeds through prediction error minimization, which shapes the network structure to generate periodic activity and make increasingly accurate predictions. The brain continuously optimizes its internal models to better predict incoming sensory information.

However, learning discrete timing relationships presents significant computational challenges. Discrete timing problems are notoriously difficult to learn in recurrent neural networks due to the credit assignment problem over empty intervals of time. Specifically, when rewards or errors occur after long delays with no intervening events, standard gradient-based learning struggles to propagate error signals backwards through the empty temporal intervals to identify which earlier states or actions were responsible [18]. It is far easier to predict a continuous periodic signal than isolated events separated by temporal gaps. This is where the vestibular cycle provides a crucial developmental scaffold: being bounced continuously along with rhythmic auditory events can support the learning of an internal model of discretely timed events without encountering the problems of temporal credit assignment.

The continuous vestibular input effectively bridges the gaps between discrete auditory events, providing a consistent training signal that guides the development of neural circuits capable of maintaining temporal predictions. This developmental account explains why vestibular-auditory integration might be fundamental to rhythm perception and production, offering a mechanism by which prenatal experience could shape postnatal rhythmic abilities.

2.5 Network Architecture and Implementation

Our theoretical framework is realized through a recurrent predictive coding network that instantiates multimodal rhythm learning. The architecture consists of three key components: a recurrent associative layer that maintains temporal predictions across empty intervals, parallel sensory pathways for auditory and vestibular inputs with separate precision-weighting, and bidirectional connections enabling both prediction generation and error propagation.

The implementation explicitly represents both hidden states and their prediction errors, enabling biologically plausible local learning without backpropagation through time. This design directly supports our developmental hypothesis: the network first learns from correlated auditory-vestibular input during training, then leverages its learned recurrent dynamics to generate appropriate vestibular predictions from auditory input alone. By encoding temporal structure in its recurrent connections, the network effectively internalizes the vestibular scaffolding that guides rhythm learning, allowing beat perception and synchronized movement to emerge naturally from predictive processing principles.

3 Methods

3.1 Network Architecture

We implemented a recurrent predictive coding network in which every hidden state x_i (white circles in figure1) is paired with an explicitly represented prediction-error unit ε_i (grey circles). Each hidden state at time step T predicts the hidden state at time step $T + 1$ via the recurrent connections, and this prediction influences the hidden state at time step $T + 1$ through prediction error minimization (see below). In addition to the recurrent network, two sensory channels converge on the associative layer: an auditory channel that conveys a binary pulse train A^t and a vestibular channel that conveys a continuous waveform V^t . Each channel is associated with a fixed precision (inverse variance) parameter— π_r for the recurrent connections, π_A for the auditory input, and π_V for the vestibular input—which gates the influence of the corresponding prediction error. No higher-order hierarchy is assumed; the model therefore isolates the minimal circuitry required for joint auditory–vestibular prediction.

Figure 1: Panel A. Precision-weighted prediction-error computation across consecutive timesteps. Two stacked time slices illustrate how the recurrent network forms predictions and computes errors from one moment ($t - 1$, yellow) to the next (t , green). In each grey column, a hidden state x_i (filled node) is partnered with its prediction-error unit ε_i (open node). Activity at time $t - 1$ is projected downward through the recurrent weight matrix θ_{ij} to generate the top-down prediction μ_i^t . The current state x_i^t is then compared with that prediction; the mismatch is scaled by the recurrent precision parameter π_r and stored in ε_i^t . Vestibular and auditory pathways operate analogously: hidden states drive predictions μ_V^t and μ_A^t via sensory weights θ_{Vj} and θ_{Aj} , and the resulting discrepancies with the observed inputs V^t and A^t are weighted by their respective precisions π_V and π_A . **Panel B. Fast state-update dynamics and local Hebbian learning driven by prediction errors.** Focusing on a single time slice t (green), this panel shows how prediction errors from panel A shape neural activity and synaptic plasticity. Each hidden state x_i receives three contributions: inhibition from its own prediction error ε_i , excitation from vestibular error ε_V gated by the weight θ_{Vi} , and excitation from auditory error ε_A gated by θ_{Ai} . The net drive determines the instantaneous rate of change of the state (\dot{x}_i), implementing a fast gradient descent on free energy within a single time step t . After this fast optimization, synaptic weights (both recurrent and sensory) are updated proportionally to the product of the postsynaptic error and the presynaptic activity—a local Hebbian rule. This slow plasticity refines future predictions, minimizing prediction error across episodes.

3.2 Generative Model and Recognition Dynamics

At every discrete timestep t , the model generates top-down predictions for the current hidden state based on the previous one, and for sensory input based on the current hidden state:

$$\mu_i^t = \sum_j \theta_{ij} \cdot f(x_j^{t-1}) \quad (1)$$

$$\mu_V^t = \sum_j \theta_{Vj} \cdot f(x_j^t) \quad (2)$$

$$\mu_A^t = \sum_j \theta_{Aj} \cdot f(x_j^t) \quad (3)$$

where $f(x)$ is a sigmoidal activation function (here tanh), and θ terms are the weights for recurrent, vestibular-associative, and auditory-associative prediction-generating connections, respectively.

Prediction errors are then computed as precision-weighted differences between predictions and actual values:

$$\varepsilon_i^t = \pi_r \cdot (x_i^t - \mu_i^t) \quad (4)$$

$$\varepsilon_V^t = \pi_V \cdot (V^t - \mu_V^t) \quad (5)$$

$$\varepsilon_A^t = \pi_A \cdot (A^t - \mu_A^t) \quad (6)$$

At each time step T , fast recognition dynamics are implemented via gradient descent on variational free energy:

$$\dot{x}_i = -\varepsilon_i^t + \varepsilon_V^t \cdot \theta_{Vi} \cdot f'(x_i^t) + \varepsilon_A^t \cdot \theta_{Ai} \cdot f'(x_i^t) \quad (7)$$

where f' is the derivative of the activation function. These dynamics drive the hidden state from a set of initial values for time step T toward values that minimize free energy (by minimizing prediction error); this final state for time step T is used as the hidden state for the purposes of subsequent weight learning and for predicting the hidden state at step $T + 1$. In this implementation, 20 Euler integration steps per external timestep was sufficient for convergence to low-error attractors.

3.3 Synaptic Plasticity

After state optimization, synaptic weights are updated by a local Hebbian rule derived from the same free-energy minimization principle:

$$\Delta\theta_{ji} = \eta \cdot \varepsilon_i^t \cdot f(x_j^{t-1}) \quad (8)$$

$$\Delta\theta_{Vj} = \eta \cdot \varepsilon_V^t \cdot f(x_j^t) \quad (9)$$

$$\Delta\theta_{Aj} = \eta \cdot \varepsilon_A^t \cdot f(x_j^t) \quad (10)$$

where η is the learning rate. Since both the error term and presynaptic activity are available locally, this learning rule is biologically plausible and does not require backpropagation through time.

3.4 Stimuli and Training Regime

During training, the network was driven by paired auditory and vestibular input streams that emulate the correlated sensory consequences of maternal locomotion:

Auditory input (A^t): A binary pulse indicating presence (1) or absence (0) of an auditory event. Events occurred every $T = 10$ timesteps. (figure 2)

Vestibular input (V^t): A symmetric triangular waveform with period T . This waveform was selected based on biomechanical evidence that trunk acceleration during human locomotion more closely resembles triangular patterns than sinusoidal ones [19]. This simulated the vestibular sensation experienced by a fetus during maternal walking. (figure 2)

Training sessions lasted 200,000 timesteps (1,000 episodes). All weights were initialized with small random values from a normal distribution $N(0, 0.05^2)$. Precision parameters during training were set as $\pi_r = 1.0$, $\pi_A = 1.0$, and $\pi_V = 1.0$.

Figure 2: Synchronized multimodal input signals used during network training. (A) Discrete auditory events occurring at regular intervals (tempo = 0.5 s). (B) Continuous triangular vestibular signal simulating the sensation of rhythmic movement. The vestibular signal completes one cycle between each auditory event, modeling the sensorimotor experience during rhythmic activities such as walking or bouncing. Vertical dashed lines indicate the temporal alignment between auditory events and the peaks of the vestibular cycle

3.5 Evaluation Conditions

After training, the network was evaluated under two conditions to assess the sufficiency of learned internal dynamics:

Auditory-only condition: Vestibular input precision was set to zero ($\pi_V = 0$), so the model received only auditory input. This tested whether vestibular predictions would still emerge. Following the theory of active inference, predictions made for a sensory channel with zero precision are assumed to be actualized through movement [20].

Silence condition: Both auditory and vestibular precision values were set to zero ($\pi_A = \pi_V = 0$), effectively removing all external sensory input. The network’s ability to sustain intrinsic dynamics was evaluated.

Recurrent precision π_r remained unchanged in both conditions.

3.6 Implementation

The model was implemented in Python using NumPy and PyTorch for matrix operations. All hyperparameters, such as learning rate and number of units, were tuned via Optuna to optimize synchronization accuracy in the auditory-only condition. Source code and data are available in the project repository.

4 Results

4.1 Multisensory Training Enables Robust Rhythm Learning

We first examined whether our predictive coding network could learn to synchronize with rhythmic patterns when provided with paired auditory and vestibular inputs. During training with auditory pulses (period $T = 10$ timesteps) accompanied by triangular vestibular waveforms, the network showed clear learning as evidenced by decreasing total prediction error (figure3 A). The combined error (sum of auditory and vestibular mean squared errors) decreased from

above 0.2 to approximately 0.12 over 6,000 training episodes, with the steepest reduction occurring in the final 2,000 episodes.

The effectiveness of this training is best demonstrated by comparing the network’s behavior before and after learning when both auditory and vestibular inputs are present (Figure 3C). Before training, the network’s vestibular predictions lagged behind the actual vestibular input (reactive), showing poor temporal alignment. After training, vestibular predictions became anticipatory, closely tracking the actual input with minimal phase lag. Similarly, auditory predictions transformed from near-zero baseline activity to showing clear anticipatory responses preceding each beat. This transformation from reactive to anticipatory processing demonstrates that the network developed an internal model capable of predicting the temporal structure of multimodal rhythmic events.

Figure 3: Learning and cross-modal prediction in multisensory rhythm training. (A) Total sensory prediction error (sum of auditory and vestibular mean squared errors) decreases during training, showing steepest reduction between episodes 4,000-6,000. (B) Training signals: synchronized auditory pulses and continuous triangular vestibular waveform used throughout training. (C) Testing with both inputs present: after training, vestibular predictions accurately track the input signal with close phase alignment, while auditory predictions become clearly anticipatory, showing activity that precedes the auditory pulses. (D) Testing with auditory-only input: spontaneous vestibular movement predictions emerge matching the training waveform despite receiving no vestibular input, demonstrating learned auditory-motor associations. Auditory predictions remain anticipatory, confirming robust cross-modal learning of underlying periodic dynamics.

4.2 Trained Network Predicts and Moves to Auditory-Only Input

To test whether training on multimodal inputs would enable cross-modal prediction, we examined the network’s response to auditory-only input after training (Figure 3D). Before training, when presented with auditory-only input (no vestibular input), the network produced no vestibular predictions and showed minimal auditory-related activity. After training,

the same auditory-only input elicited dramatically different behavior: the network spontaneously generated vestibular predictions matching the triangular waveform from training, despite receiving no vestibular input. Additionally, auditory predictions became anticipatory, showing activity preceding actual auditory pulses.

This cross-modal prediction demonstrates that the network learned a unified internal model of periodic underlying dynamics that link auditory and vestibular streams. Under active inference principles, these vestibular predictions in the absence of vestibular input constitute motor commands—the system predicts sensory consequences of movement that, in biological systems, would drive actual motor output to fulfill the prediction. This provides a computational account for why hearing rhythmic patterns spontaneously evokes the urge to move.

4.3 Continuous Vestibular Signals Are Necessary for Rhythm Learning

To test whether continuous vestibular input was necessary for successful learning, we conducted control experiments using a "pulse training" paradigm in which discrete auditory pulses were provided to both sensory channels, keeping all hyperparameters and training conditions identical to the standard training. Under pulse training conditions, the network failed to learn stable rhythmic representations. During pulse training with discrete auditory pulses on both the auditory and vestibular channels, total prediction error showed no systematic decrease over 7,000 training episodes, instead exhibiting irregular fluctuations and even increases in later training (figure4 A).

The failure of learning is evident when comparing network behavior before and after pulse training (figure4 B). Even after 7,000 episodes, the network showed no anticipatory behavior—auditory predictions remained reactive and poorly aligned with actual inputs, similar to the untrained state. Using identical network architecture and hyperparameters, this control condition demonstrates that discrete pulses alone cannot support rhythm learning.

This failure highlights a fundamental challenge in learning discrete timing: without continuous signals bridging the silent intervals between auditory pulses, the network cannot assign credit across temporal gaps. The vestibular waveform thus serves as a critical scaffold, transforming a difficult discrete timing problem into a more tractable continuous prediction task.

Figure 4: Failure of rhythm learning without continuous vestibular training signal. (A) During pulse training with discrete auditory pulses on both the auditory and vestibular channels using identical hyperparameters and conditions as standard training, total prediction error shows no systematic decrease over 7,000 episodes. (B) Training input: identical discrete pulses provided to both vestibular and auditory channels. (C) After training with pulse inputs: network behavior remains reactive without anticipation even after extensive training, demonstrating that the same network architecture cannot learn rhythm from discrete pulses alone. Compare with Figure 3B-C, where continuous vestibular input enables successful learning.

4.4 Internal Dynamics Sustain Rhythm in the Absence of Input

To assess whether learned rhythms could persist without external timing cues, we set the auditory input to zero after initial entrainment while maintaining the same temporal structure (figure5). The network continued generating coherent oscillatory vestibular predictions for over 100 timesteps following the cessation of meaningful auditory input. While the amplitude of these predictions gradually decreased over time, the phase coherence remained intact throughout the continuation period, maintaining the same period as the training rhythm.

This sustained internal activity reveals that the recurrent connections developed during training can maintain temporal patterns without any external pacing signal. The network’s ability to continue the rhythm when auditory input becomes silent (zero values) mirrors how humans can internally maintain a beat after music stops.

Figure 5: Internal rhythm continuation after auditory input cessation. Top: Auditory input set to zero at transition point (dashed line). Bottom: Network’s vestibular predictions continue for over 100 timesteps with gradually decreasing amplitude but maintained phase coherence, demonstrating autonomous rhythm generation through learned recurrent dynamics.

5 Discussion

Our computational model demonstrates two interrelated phenomena that shed light on the developmental origins of human rhythmic abilities. First, continuous vestibular input provides valuable scaffolding for learning discrete rhythmic patterns, solving the temporal credit assignment problem inherent in learning structure underlying sparse temporal patterns. Second, the pairing of vestibular and auditory inputs during training leads to cross-modal predictions that, under active inference principles, would spontaneously generate movement to rhythm. Together, these findings offer a mechanistic account of how prenatal and early postnatal experience might shape both rhythm perception and the universal human tendency to move to music.

5.1 Theoretical Implications for Vestibular-Auditory Integration

The critical role of vestibular input in our model aligns with accumulating evidence for vestibular contributions to rhythm perception. Todd and colleagues have long argued that the vestibular system plays a fundamental role in rhythm perception, proposing that low-frequency sound can directly activate vestibular organs and that this activation contributes to the perception of musical beat [21, 22]. Our model extends this work by showing how vestibular signals might not just contribute to rhythm perception but actually facilitate its development through predictive learning.

The model’s behavior also resonates with the seminal findings of Phillips-Silver and Trainor [8, 23], who demonstrated that vestibular input shapes auditory rhythm encoding in both infants and adults. When bounced on every second versus every third beat, listeners encode identical auditory patterns as either duple or triple meter, respectively. Our model provides a computational framework for understanding this phenomenon: the predictive coding network learns joint auditory-vestibular representations where the phase and period of vestibular input fundamentally shape how auditory patterns are encoded and predicted.

This model makes predictions that may be tractable in observational experiments. If audio-vestibular associations are indeed a primary cause of the desire to move to auditory rhythm, then we would predict that infants whose mothers were on bed rest during their gestation would show less spontaneous movement to music. We would be very interested to see this possibility explored in future work. Impairment might also be observable in early beat perception skills, as measured by EEG; however, this prediction runs into the possible confound of increased music listening during bed rest, which could itself help to scaffold beat perception (and has been offered as a possible explanation for the surprising

observation of more instrumentalists among children whose mothers were confined to bed for a period during their gestation [24]).

5.2 Limitations and Scope

It is important to note that we are not claiming beat perception is exclusively learned through maternal gait. Rather, our model demonstrates that maternal locomotion can serve as one helpful scaffold among many for developing rhythm perception abilities. The correlated auditory and vestibular inputs from maternal walking provide a naturalistic training signal that may bootstrap the development of neural circuits for rhythm processing, but other multisensory experiences and evolved rhythm-specific circuitry likely contribute as well. Indeed, other modeling work has argued that the foundations of rhythm perception are intrinsically oscillatory brain circuits [25], and that the development of rhythm perception through coordinated auditory and vestibular input is better viewed as experience-dependent refinement of these innate brain circuits [26].

Furthermore, while our model demonstrates that auditory-only input can generate vestibular predictions that could drive movement under active inference principles, we acknowledge that such predictions may serve multiple functions beyond generating an urge to move. The same learned cross-modal predictions could also support other functions that do not require overt movement— for example, vestibular predictions in time with the sound of others’ footsteps could help to infer gait speed or to differentiate conspecific from non-conspecific gait in the absence of visual cues. We therefore interpret the "urge to move" as one plausible expression of the learned generative model rather than a required outcome on every presentation of rhythmic input.

Our model also simplifies the complexity of natural walking patterns. Real maternal gait contains considerable variability, with stops, starts, and fluctuations in tempo that we did not capture in our perfectly isochronous training signals. Whether learning from more realistic, variable walking patterns would generalize to the near-perfect isochrony of musical rhythms remains untested. Conversely, if the urge to move originates from learning based on naturalistic walking input with its inherent variability, this might predict stronger movement responses to rhythms with microtiming variations rather than metronomic beats. Future work should examine how the model performs with more ecologically valid input patterns that capture the natural variability of human locomotion.

The simplicity of our single-layer architecture also imposes constraints on the model’s current capabilities. The model currently handles only a single tempo, whereas human rhythm perception operates across a range of frequencies and can flexibly switch between different metric interpretations of the same stimulus. It models only entrainment to a periodic pulse, leaving out our characteristic capacity to entrain periodic movements to complex rhythms. Additionally, the network produces somewhat smoothed predictions rather than the precise predictions characteristic of beat perception in humans.

5.3 Future Directions

Several extensions could address current limitations and expand the model’s explanatory scope. Implementing a hierarchical architecture with multiple layers would introduce additional nonlinearity, enabling sharper temporal predictions. With multiple layers of nonlinear transformations, the network could apply more complex, precise functions to its internal states, allowing it to make highly specific predictions at particular phase values. The inclusion of nonlinear activation functions with steeper gradients could also improve temporal precision.

Extending the model to train and predict at multiple tempos represents an important challenge that could be addressed through hierarchical architecture. To handle multiple tempos, the network would likely need higher layers to maintain an abstract representation of tempo as a variable state, changing on a slower timescale relative to the unfolding phase. This hierarchical organization would allow the network to learn tempo flexibility through a process of generalization. Notably, such a developmental trajectory aligns with empirical observations: young children’s synchronized movement is initially limited to a narrow range of gait-like tempos (typically 100-130 BPM) [27, 28] and carrying cadence has both short and long-term influences on infant spontaneous motor tempo [29, 30], suggesting that early rhythm perception may indeed be promoted and/or constrained by early locomotor experience. A developmental model could start with a limited tempo range and gradually expand through experience with diverse rhythmic inputs. This influence of early movement experience on rhythm perception may continue into adulthood, as body size and movement experience shape preferred beat rates throughout life [31, 32]

Perhaps most intriguingly, the framework could be extended to complex rhythms. Recent evidence suggests that vestibular input on strong beats actually shapes our perception of complex rhythms, potentially helping us learn to parse their temporal structure. This is supported by studies showing that physical movement [8, 23] and even galvanic vestibular stimulation without actual movement [33] can bias meter perception, demonstrating the fundamental role of

vestibular input in rhythm processing. By incorporating beat-based vestibular input into our model, we could train a network to recognize and anticipate even complex rhythmic patterns, with vestibular sensation serving as an anchor that helps parse temporal structure.

In this context, rhythmic density itself can provide scaffolding for learning precise predictions by partially solving the temporal credit assignment problem that plagues sparse isochronous patterns. Just as continuous vestibular input helps bridge temporal gaps between beats in simple patterns, the additional events in complex rhythms could serve a similar scaffolding function. If vestibular input on strong beats helps establish a metric framework, the intervening rhythmic complexity could fill temporal gaps much like the continuous vestibular signal does in our current model. This would predict that complex rhythms with clear metric anchors might actually facilitate learning compared to simple but temporally sparse patterns.

5.4 Broader Implications

Our findings contribute to understanding why rhythmic abilities appear uniquely developed in humans compared to other primates. The bipedal locomotion hypothesis [34] proposes that upright walking created selective pressure for rhythm perception, but our model suggests a more direct developmental mechanism: the sensory consequences of bipedal gait, experienced even before birth, may actively shape neural circuits for rhythm processing through predictive learning.

This developmental account has potential clinical implications. Developmental conditions affecting vestibular function or sensorimotor integration (e.g. Developmental Coordination Disorder [35]) might impact rhythm perception abilities, and early interventions incorporating coordinated auditory-vestibular stimulation could potentially support rhythm development. The model also suggests why movement-based music education methods like Dalcroze Eurhythmics [36], which explicitly couple auditory rhythm with whole-body movement, may be particularly effective.

6 Conclusion

By implementing a minimal predictive coding circuit that learns from naturalistic multisensory experience, we have shown how two puzzling aspects of human musicality—the ability to find structure in temporally disjointed auditory patterns and the spontaneous urge to move to them—may emerge from the same computational principles. The model demonstrates that neither sophisticated neural machinery nor explicit teaching signals are necessary; rather, the simple experience of correlated auditory and vestibular inputs, such as those provided by maternal gait, can give rise to both rhythm perception and rhythmic movement. This work bridges evolutionary, developmental, and computational perspectives on human rhythm, offering a unified account of why we alone among primates cannot help but move to the beat.

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